

Influence of length and sensor positioning on acoustic time-of-flight measurement in structural timber

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ABSTRACT

The mechanical properties of timber can be estimated from wave propagation velocity by measuring wave time-of-flight. However, a time lag has been observed in wave time of flight in previous works. This effect produces an apparent velocity dependency on length, and it is due to several factors such as species, knottiness and the device used. This research aims to determine this time lag using different sensor positionings for in situ time of flight measurements.

Time-of-flight longitudinal measurements were conducted on 120 90×140 mm specimens of four Spanish coniferous species: radiata pine, Scots pine, lario pine and maritime pine. Three commercially available acoustic devices were used: Sylvatest Duo, USLab, and Microsecond Timer. Different sensor placement arrangements were used: end-to-end measurement, measurement in the same surface and on opposite surfaces. Time-of-flight data were obtained from the full-length (4 m) specimens, and then from the same specimens cut to 3, 2, and 1 metre long.

Empirical models were developed for the relationship between time-of-flight measurements and timber lengths in the range of 1 to 4 m. Surface and crossed measurements were compared with end-to-end measurement to validate the time lag procedure.

KEYWORDS: Non-destructive testing, Sensors positioning, Stress-Wave, Time-of-flight, Time lag, Ultrasound wave.

1. INTRODUCTION

Acoustic wave technology has been used to assess the mechanical properties of structural timber for decades, and it is mainly based on predicting the modulus of elasticity (MOE) of wood through longitudinal acoustic wave measurements. It is important to note that acoustic measurements in timber are affected by many factors, such as moisture content, temperature, dimension of the timber piece, test procedures, and the instruments used (James 1961, Gerhards 1982a, Bucur and Böhnke 1994, Wang 2013, Íñiguez-González et al. 2015).

Specimen geometry has a significant effect on wave propagation mode and acoustic velocity in structural timber. Several researchers investigated the influence of piece geometry (cross-section size, length and ratios between their dimensions) on non-destructive prediction of the mechanical properties of timber.

Bucur (1984) conducted acoustic measurements on spruce (*Picea abies* L. Karst.) timber specimens with different width-to-thickness ratios (b/h , from 1 to 14) concluding that acoustic velocity was greatly affected by this ratio. The higher the ratio, the slower the velocity. In another study, longitudinal velocity was nearly constant when the length-to-width ratio was varied from 20 to 40 (Bucur 1984).

The influence of cross-section size and length on ultrasonic measurements in *Eucalyptus sp.* specimens was studied (Bartholomeu et al. 2003). They concluded that a minimum length of specimen should be specified, depending on the operating frequencies of the ultrasonic sensors used. Ultrasonic measurements can be performed when (length-to-wavelength ratio) $L/\lambda > 5$. This requirement is included in the Brazilian non-destructive test standard NBR 15521 (2007). A similar study of the effect of specimen length on ultrasonic measurement investigated the variation of velocity in structural lumber of four different species (Oliveira et al. 2006). The authors reported that specimen length-to-wavelength ratio (L/λ) clearly affected measured wave velocity when L/λ was less than 3. The wave velocity remained relatively unchanged when L/λ was greater than 3.

Divos et al. (2005) determined longitudinal wave velocity in tapered pieces by the acoustic resonance-based method. They found higher longitudinal wave velocity when the width ratio between ends was greater. The results of ultrasound velocity measurements with a Sylvatest Duo device (22 kHz) on 161 specimens of missanda (*Erythrophleum spp.*) showed that length has a much greater influence than cross-section on time-of-flight (ToF) measurement. Apparent longitudinal velocity decreased by 83 m s^{-1} as length increased by 1 m in the range of 1.6 m to 7.1 m (Arriaga et al. 2006). Acuña et al. (2007) studied acoustic longitudinal wave velocity in 5 species; the authors proposed species-specific factors for angle and length adjustment of the apparent velocity.

The influence of specimen length and knottiness was studied using ultrasound measurements (Sylvatest Duo device, 22 kHz) in Spanish Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.). As specimen length increased 1 m, apparent velocity decreased by $68 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ in unknotty timber and $83 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ in knotty timber (Íñiguez et al. 2007). Thus, knottiness affected ToF measurements in the same species. This influence of wood quality on ToF was also observed in later works (Íñiguez-González et al. 2015).

Some correction factors were proposed for ultrasound velocity in structural sawn Spanish Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) and laricio pine (*Pinus nigra* Arn.) timber measured by the Sylvatest Duo (Arriaga et al. 2009). The effect of cross-section size of square Douglas fir (*Pseudotsuga menziesii* Mirb. Franco) timber on dynamic MOE was studied (Wang 2013). It was concluded that different sizes of timber should not be graded together without making appropriate adjustments on dynamic MOE for the size effect. Recent works focused on timber strength grading using acoustic methods (Arriaga et al. 2012, Casado et al. 2012, Vega et al. 2012, Pommieret al. 2013). Vega et al. (2012) found that known piece length can improve the prediction of mechanical properties when using acoustic wave transmission velocity.

This apparent length dependency of velocity can be explained by a time lag effect on ToF measurements (Llana et al. 2013), and can be easily corrected by a simple adjustment procedure of ToF measurements (Llana et al. 2016). ToF measurements are usually done from end-to-end of the test piece under laboratory conditions, but in the practical assessment of existing structures end-to-end measurements are not possible and other sensor positions must be used. Measuring ToF after placing the sensors on timber piece surfaces is a typical procedure in existing timber structure assessment. The effect of the position of the receiver sensor on the stress wave has been studied by several authors (Gerhards 1980, 1982b, Arriaga et al. 2015). In particular, the sensor positioning effect on time lag determination was studied in a previous work on Scots pine species and ultrasound measurements using the Sylvatest Duo (Arriaga et al. 2016).

The aim of this work is to propose a procedure to determine the time lag by means of in situ ToF measurements using different sensor positions (surface and crossed measurements) comparing the results with direct measurements (end-to-end measurements). This was studied in four Spanish sourced coniferous species using several commercially available ultrasonic/stress wave devices. The results of this procedure were compared with those obtained by direct (end-to-end) measurement.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Material and specimen preparation

The materials used in this study were 120 pieces of structural timber from four different pine species grown in Spain (30 pieces of each species): radiata pine (*Pinus radiata* D. Don), Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.), laricio pine (*Pinus nigra* ssp. *salzmannii* (Dunal) Franco), and maritime pine (*Pinus pinaster* Ait. ssp. *mesogeensis* Fieschi&Gaussen). All specimens were air-dried and planed to 90 mm by 140 mm by 4000 mm.

The experiment was designed to test timber specimens of four different lengths, starting from an initial length of 4 m, then decreasing to 3 m, 2 m, and 1 m. Following the initial acoustic longitudinal measurements on the 4 m timber specimens, a 0.5 m section was cut from both ends of each piece of timber to obtain a length of 3 m. This procedure was repeated two more times to obtain timber specimens 2 m and 1 m long, Figure 1. The length to width ratio varied from 44 to 11.

Figure 1. Preparation of specimens

2.2 Visual strength grading

All timber specimens were visually graded according to Spanish standard UNE 56544 (2011) at their initial 4 m length. This standard establishes the visual grade (MEG) for timber pieces with a width greater than 70 mm. The resulting MEG grades of the timber pieces vary greatly from 17% to 97%, Table 1.

The timber grading process assesses knottiness, which is characterized by the concentrated knot diameter ratio, or CKDR (Divos and Tanaka 1997). The knot diameter ratio (KDR) is defined as the knot diameter divided by the depth or width of the piece in Japanese standard SIS-19 1991. The concentrated knot diameter ratio (CKDR) is the sum of the KDRs of the knots existing in any 15 cm length of a piece of timber. The distance defining a knot cluster is set at 15 cm by EN 844-9 (1997). The maximum CKDR observed on all 4 faces represents the quality of the piece, Figure 2. The CKDR value was obtained for the worst 15 cm section in the entire piece, ranging from 0 to 1. Table 1 also shows the mean and maximum values of grain slope in 4 m long timber pieces. This grain deviation was measured in a 1 m length according to the visual grading standard, disregarding local deviations due to knots.

Table 1. Visual grade percentage according to Spanish standard UNE 56544, CKDR by length group and slope of grain in 4 m long timber pieces

Species	MEG grade (%)	Mean CKDR per specimen's length group				Slope of grain (%)	
		4 (m)	3 (m)	2 (m)	1 (m)	mean	min.-max.
radiata pine	66	0.17	0.15	0.13	0.12	2.5	0-6.5
Scots pine	97	0.13	0.13	0.12	0.10	1.9	0-7.8
laricio pine	63	0.18	0.17	0.16	0.14	2.6	0-12.1
maritime pine	17	0.28	0.25	0.23	0.16	9.1	0-19.5

Figure 2. Concentrated knot diameter ratio; republished from Iñiguez (2007) with permission

2.3 Time-of-flight measurement

ToF acoustic longitudinal measurements were conducted on all specimens of four different lengths using three commercial instruments: 1) Sylvatest Duo (CBS-CBT, France-Switzerland) with conical 22 kHz sensors; 2) USLab (Agricef, Campinas, Brazil) with conical 45 kHz sensors; and 3) MicroSecond Timer (MST) (Fakopp Enterprise, Sopron, Hungary), an impact-induced stress wave timing device. Devices 1 and 2 are considered ultrasonic devices because excitation is by piezoelectric sensor with a specific ultrasonic frequency (sensor frequency). On the other hand, device 3 is considered to be a stress-wave device because the excitation is by a hammer.

Measurements were performed using five different sensor placement arrangements, Figure 3: a) Direct measurement (longitudinal or parallel to the axis of the piece) by placing sensors at each end of the specimen; this measurement was used to determine end-to-end or parallel velocity (V_0); b) and c) Surface measurement by placing both sensors on the same edge and on the same face, deducing the surface velocities (V_{se} and V_{sf} , respectively); and, d) Crossed measurement, by placing a sensor on one edge and the other on the opposite edge, obtaining the crossed velocity from edge to opposite edge (V_{ce}); and finally, e) Crossed measurement by placing one sensor on one face and the other on the opposite face, obtaining the crossed velocity from face to opposite face (V_{cf}).

Figure 3. Sensor placement arrangements: a) Parallel to the grain; b) Surface measurement on the same edge; c) Surface measurement on the same face; d) Crossed measurement between opposite edges; and, d) Crossed measurement between opposite faces.

Surface measurements were taken only in one of the surface edges of the piece (and one of the faces) which were chosen at random. Also, similarly, crossed measurements were taken from one of the edges to the opposite one (and from one of the faces to the opposite one). These too were chosen at random.

Surface and crossed measurements were performed by placing the sensors at a distance of 240 mm from the end of the piece to avoid any possible border effect. Two measurement points were considered for each arrangement, located at thirds of the depth of the piece, except in edge measurement where due to narrowness only one centred measurement was made, Figure 4. The mean value of both measurements was considered for calculations.

Figure 4. Sensor positioning

Sensor orientation in crossed and surface measurements was at an angle equal to or slightly less than 45° with respect to the timber surface. ToF and velocity in surface measurement were thereby obtained for each length (3.52, 2.52, 1.52 and 0.52 m) on the edges (V_{se}) and on the faces (V_{sf}).

Finally the crossed measurements were recorded. These too were between cross-sections separated at distances of 3.52, 2.52, 1.52 and 0.52 m. These lengths correspond to slightly longer distances between sensors, and the lines joining the sensors form an angle with respect to the axis of the piece varying from 1.47° to 15.07° , Table 2.

Table 2. Distances and angles with respect to the axis of the piece, in crossed measurements

Length (m)	Opposite edges		Opposite faces	
	Distance (m)	Angle ($^\circ$)	Distance (m)	Angle ($^\circ$)
3.52	3.523	2.28	3.521	1.47
2.52	2.524	3.18	2.522	2.05
1.52	1.526	5.26	1.523	3.39
0.52	0.538	15.07	0.528	9.82

2.4 Static modulus of elasticity, density and moisture content

The static modulus of elasticity (MOE) of timber pieces was determined by the static bending test according to European Standard EN 408 (2010+A1:2012). The test piece is simply supported and symmetrically loaded in bending at thirds of a span equal to 18 times the depth of the piece, Figure 5. This test was performed when the timber pieces were 3 m long. Table 3 shows the mean values for each species.

Figure 5. Arrangement for bending test according to European Standard EN 408 (2010+A1:2012)

The actual dimensions and weight of each specimen were measured, and the density was determined based on the weight and volume at the time of acoustic testing. The mean values were from 517 to 573 kg m⁻³, Table 3.

The moisture content (MC) of the timber specimens was measured using an electrical resistance moisture meter (Gann RTU600, Gann Mess-u, RegeltechnikGmbH, Germany) according to the EN 13183-2 (2002) standard. Table 3 shows the corresponding values for each species group.

Table 3. Species MOE, density and MC

Species	MOE		Density		MC	
	Mean (N mm ⁻²)	COV (%)	Mean (kg m ⁻³)	COV (%)	Mean (%)	COV (%)
radiata pine	10746	16.5	517	6.2	10.1	8.7
Scots pine	11776	11.7	523	8.5	9.1	9.0
laricio pine	11870	21.7	548	9.2	11.9	7.2
maritime pine	8534	19.5	573	9.5	9.8	12.3

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 End to end measurements

Velocity and distance

The apparent velocity of wave transmission was obtained by dividing measured length by recorded ToF. Figure 6 shows the means plot of this velocity (V_{app}) for each length (1, 2, 3 and 4 m) and for four examples of the total number of case combinations (four species and three devices). The velocity apparently slightly decreases as length increases. This tendency was observed in all cases (all combinations of the four species and the three devices). A linear regression was established between velocity and length for each combination. There was a statistically significant relationship between velocity and length, at a confidence level of 95%, because P was lower than 0.05 in all cases (0.0000 to 0.0026, mean value 0.0007). Theoretically and assuming that the properties of wood are constant along the length of the piece, velocity should be independent of length. However, these results show a slight opposite tendency, as was shown in previous studies (Lana et al. 2016).

Figure 6. Means plot of apparent velocity ANOVA for length corresponding to four species and device combinations

Time lag correction

This apparent dependency of velocity on length is due to a time lag in measured time which depends on the characteristics of the device used and timber singularities (Llana et al. 2016). The time lag can be obtained establishing a linear regression between ToF and length, equation (1).

$$\text{ToF} = a + b \cdot L \quad (1)$$

Where b is the slope and a is the ordinate axis value at the intersection with the straight line, which, in all cases, was negative (-12.54 to -34.04) with a high determination coefficient ($r^2 = 0.95$ to 0.98). Figure 7 shows an example for radiata pine; in this case, the intersection of the line with the ordinate axis occurs at a time equal to $-15.06 \mu\text{s}$. Therefore, the measured times must be corrected by adding this time lag.

Figure 7. Example of linear regression between ToF and length for radiata pine species and the MicroSecond Timer device

This time lag correction was applied to all the species and device combinations. Figure 8 shows the means plot of the velocity, corrected by the respective time lag, obtained in 4 examples. All cases present a similar pattern: velocity for 2 to 4 m length is

approximately constant, except for the 1 m length which shows a lower value with statistically significant differences in half of the cases.

Figure 8. Means plot of velocity ANOVA (including time lag correction) for length corresponding to four cases of species and device combination

Some studies conclude that a minimum specimen length should be specified, depending on the operating frequencies of the ultrasonic sensors used. The effect of specimen length on ultrasonic measurement was studied by several researchers. Oliveira et al. (2006) investigated the variation of ultrasonic velocity (22 kHz) in 50 by 120 mm structural timber of four different species (*Pinus caribaea* Morelet., *Eucalyptus citriodora* Hook., *Eucalyptus grandis* Hill. ex Maid. and *Hymenaea sp.*) with lengths ranging from 0.1 to 3 m. These authors reported a clear effect of specimen length-to-wavelength ratio (L/λ) on measured wave velocity when L/λ was under 3. Wave velocity was found to be relatively unchanged when L/λ was above 3. Similarly, Bartholomeu et al. (2003) examined the influence of cross-section size and length on ultrasonic measurements in *Eucalyptus sp.* specimens using a Steinkamp BP7 (Ultratest, Germany) with 45 kHz transducers. They concluded that ultrasonic measurements can be performed when $L/\lambda > 5$.

In this case, and assuming a velocity of 5000 m/s, the wave length was approximately $\lambda = 0.23$ and 0.11 m for the Sylvatest Duo and UsLab devices, respectively ($\lambda = V/f = 5000/22 \cdot 10^3$ and $5000/45 \cdot 10^3$). Thus the minimum specimen length should be $L \geq 5 \cdot \lambda = 1.15$ and 0.55 m. The MicroSecond Timer is a stress-wave device because excitation is by a hammer. The frequency of the wave detected by the stop sensor is unknown. Therefore, the previous reasons in connection with the distance-wavelength ratio cannot explain the different velocity values for 1 m long pieces. But hereinafter measurements for 1 m long pieces were discarded.

The time lag was again obtained by establishing a linear regression between ToF and length, but excluding 1 m long piece measurements. Table 4 shows the linear regression coefficients according to equation (1).

Table 4. Linear regression models for ToF vs. length (equation 1, for lengths: 2, 3 and 4 m)

Species	Sylvatest Duo			USLab			MST Fakopp		
	a (μs)	b ($m^{-1} \mu s$)	r^2	a (μs)	b ($m^{-1} \mu s$)	r^2	a (μs)	b ($m^{-1} \mu s$)	r^2
radiata pine	-30.61	199.44	0.95	-28.07	182.55	0.95	-19.32	191.14	0.95
Scots pine	-23.02	195.92	0.95	-27.48	181.49	0.95	-20.62	195.37	0.96
laricio pine	-41.42	208.02	0.96	-36.97	188.39	0.96	-39.36	200.95	0.97
maritime pine	-58.76	241.30	0.90	-63.23	224.48	0.90	-39.04	229.75	0.91

This time lag correction was applied to all the species and device combinations. Figure 9 shows the means graph of the velocity obtained with time lag correction deduced from equation (1) and Table 4, for each length (2, 3 and 4 m) for four examples. The velocity shows an approximately constant value for the three lengths in all species and device combinations. There is no statistically significant relation between velocity and length, at a confidence level of 95%, because P value (0.4994 to 0.9773, mean value 0.7869) is greater than 0.05.

Figure 9. Means plot of velocity ANOVA (including time lag correction) for length (2 - 4 m) corresponding to four cases of species and device combination

The mean value of velocity corrected by the time lag can be obtained for each species and device as the inverse of term b indicated in table 4 from equation (1). Table 5 shows the mean values of the velocities obtained for each species, device and length (V_i), and it also includes the velocity corrected by time lag (V_{cor}) named as “independent” of length in the table.

Table 5. Mean values of time lag corrected velocity (V_{cor}) for each species and device, and apparent velocity (V_i) for each species, device and length

Species	Symbol	Length (m)	Velocity ($m s^{-1}$)		
			Sylvatest Duo	USLab	MST Fakopp
	V_{cor}	-	5014	5478	5232
radiata pine	V_4	4	5227	5704	5392
	V_3	3	5328	5839	5421
	V_2	2	5434	5921	5539
	V_1	1	5642	6116	5698

Scots pine	V _{cor}	-	5104	5510	5118
	V ₄	4	5275	5734	5270
	V ₃	3	5340	5867	5332
	V ₂	2	5434	5946	5409
	V ₁	1	5568	6088	5485
laricio pine	V _{cor}	-	4807	5308	4976
	V ₄	4	5072	5586	5229
	V ₃	3	5176	5735	5382
	V ₂	2	5348	5871	5496
	V ₁	1	5434	5980	5748
maritime pine	V _{cor}	-	4144	4455	4353
	V ₄	4	4435	4820	4570
	V ₃	3	4596	5014	4680
	V ₂	2	4721	5188	4765
	V ₁	1	4839	5283	4975

The ratio V_i/V_{cor} is greater than 1 and it represents the error in the estimation of velocity, which becomes lower as the length increases. A multiple linear regression was calculated between this ratio and species, length, device and knottiness for each length (CKDR), equation (2) with a determination coefficient of 0.90.

$$V_i/V_{cor} = 1.221 - 0.29 \cdot CKDR - 0.0199 \cdot L + 0.0151 \cdot D_s + 0.0218 \cdot D_u - 0.0732 \cdot S_r - 0.0887 \cdot S_s - 0.0424 \cdot S_l \quad (2)$$

L is the length of measurement in m;

D_s and D_u are the device qualitative parameters; $D_s = 1$ for Sylvatest Duo, $D_u = 1$ for USLab, and 0 in other case; $D_s = D_u = 0$ for MST Fakopp;

S_r , S_s and S_l are the species qualitative parameters; $S_r = 1$ for radiate, $S_s = 1$ for Scots and $S_l = 1$ for laricio, and 0 in other case; $S_r = S_s = S_l = 0$ for maritime pine.

Table 6 shows the standard errors and P-values for each parameter. There was a statistically significant relation between the ratio of velocities and all parameters at a confidence level of 95%, because P-values are smaller than 0.05. The highest P-value corresponds to CKDR at 0.027.

Table 6. Standard error and P-values in equation (2).

Parameter	Standard Error	P-value
Constant	0.023630	0.0000
CKDR	0.126283	0.0270
Length	0.002928	0.0000
D_s	0.004337	0.0012
D_u	0.004337	0.0000
S_r	0.012132	0.0000
S_s	0.014766	0.0000
S_l	0.009886	0.0001

3.2 Surface measurements

Velocity and distance

The same procedure used in end-to-end measurements was followed and the same length effect was observed in surface measurement. The 0.52 m length was discarded for the reasons described in previous section. The measurements were made in the edge and on the face surface of the piece, considering three lengths: 1.52, 2.52 and 3.52 m.

Time lag correction

The time lag was obtained by establishing a linear regression between ToF and length (1.52, 2.52 and 3.52 m), for edge-to-edge measurements and for face-to-face measurements. Table 7 shows the linear regression coefficients according to equation (1).

Table 7. Linear regression models for ToF vs. length (equation 1, for lengths: 1.52, 2.52 and 3.52 m). Surface measurements

	Species	Sylvatest Duo			USLab			MST Fakopp		
		a (μs)	b ($\text{m}^{-1} \mu\text{s}$)	r^2	a (μs)	b ($\text{m}^{-1} \mu\text{s}$)	r^2	a (μs)	b ($\text{m}^{-1} \mu\text{s}$)	r^2
Edge to edge	radiata p.	-27.86	206.32	0.95	-32.35	191.91	0.95	-13.24	191.17	0.96
	Scots p.	-23.47	202.17	0.96	-32.59	188.45	0.96	-17.02	197.90	0.97
	laricio p.	-48.29	217.29	0.96	-48.55	198.39	0.96	-34.04	202.94	0.97
	maritime p.	-39.41	243.11	0.92	-48.97	230.48	0.92	-15.85	227.64	0.93
Face to face	radiata p.	-27.71	206.46	0.96	-24.96	187.29	0.95	-12.37	192.57	0.96
	Scots p.	-6.43	198.60	0.96	-18.22	184.76	0.96	-8.05	196.20	0.97
	laricio p.	-27.37	212.93	0.97	-33.76	195.84	0.97	-30.52	204.24	0.97
	maritime p.	-46.25	247.08	0.92	-55.19	232.95	0.92	-24.48	230.22	0.93

This time lag (coefficient a in table 7) correction was applied to all the combinations of species and devices. Figure 10 shows the means plot of the velocity obtained with time lag correction deduced from equation (1) and Table 7, for each length (1.52, 2.52 and 3.52 m) for four examples. The velocity shows an approximately constant value for the three lengths in all combinations of species and device. There is no statistically significant relationship between corrected velocity and length, at a confidence level of 95%, because P -values (0.1911 to 0.9973, mean value 0.6247) are greater than 0.05.

Figure 10. Means plot of velocity ANOVA (including time lag correction) for length (1.52, 2.52 and 3.52 m) in surface measurements corresponding to four cases of species and device combination

3.3 Crossed measurements

Velocity, distance and angle

The crossed ToF measurements showed a similar length effect to previous arrangements (end-to-end and surface measurements). The measurements were made between opposite edges and opposite faces of the piece, considering three lengths (distances between two cross-sections of the piece): 1.52, 2.52 and 3.52 m. The 0.52 m length was discarded for the same reasons described in section 3.1.

The angle between the lines joining sensors and the axis of the piece was from 2.28° to 5.26° in edge to edge measurement, and from 1.47° to 3.39° in face to face measurement, Table 2. Further, there were 3 measurements distances (3.523, 2.524 and 1.526 m for edge measurements and 3.521, 2.522 and 1.523 m for face measurements).

It is important to take into account that grain slopes in trees due to the trunk tapering and in some cases due to spiral grain. This deviation of grain is translated to a timber piece with some variations depending on the sawing pattern. It consists of a deviation in fibre direction with respect to the axis of the piece. In the typical structural grade MEG according to the Spanish visual grading standard UNE 56544:2011, the maximum permitted slope of grain is 1:6 (equivalent to 9°). The slope of grain in the analysed timber pieces varies depending on the species, Table 1. The mean angle was 1.45°, 1.10°, 1.51° and 5.18° for radiata, Scots, laricio and maritime pine, respectively.

In the crossed measurements, the angle of the deviation of grain and the angle formed between both sensors are added or subtracted depending on the particular disposition on each piece. The effects of the angle and of the length are mixed and it is not possible to separate their effects. In any case, the values of angles were below 5.26°. Time lag was therefore determined without taking into account the angle between the line joining the sensors and the axis of the piece.

Time lag correction

The time lag was obtained by establishing a linear regression between ToF and distance (1.523, 2.524 and 3.523 m), for edge to opposite edge measurements, and (3.521, 2.522 and 1.523 m) for face to opposite face measurements. Table 8 shows the coefficients of linear regressions according to equation (1).

Table 8. Linear regression models for ToF vs. length (equation 1, for lengths: 1.52, 2.52 and 3.52 m). Crossed measurements

	Species	Sylvatest Duo			USLab			MST Fakopp		
		a (μs)	b ($m^{-1} \mu s$)	r^2	a (μs)	b ($m^{-1} \mu s$)	r^2	a (μs)	b ($m^{-1} \mu s$)	r^2
Edge to edge	radiata p.	-20.35	204.60	0.95	-21.42	188.66	0.95	-3.65	191.08	0.96
	Scots p.	-11.33	199.30	0.96	-16.35	184.54	0.95	+1.348	193.00	0.97
	laricio p.	-25.20	211.17	0.96	-31.46	195.56	0.95	-15.83	198.62	0.97
	maritime p.	-44.10	247.32	0.92	-51.60	232.39	0.92	-16.23	227.92	0.92
Face to face	radiata p.	-27.84	206.23	0.96	-22.15	186.69	0.95	-8.34	191.38	0.96
	Scots p.	-12.62	200.19	0.96	-21.53	185.55	0.96	-9.42	195.49	0.97
	laricio p.	-32.26	215.04	0.97	-35.01	197.14	0.96	-30.68	204.00	0.97
	maritime p.	-39.43	244.67	0.92	-49.74	231.17	0.92	-22.24	230.23	0.93

This time lag (coefficient a in table 8) correction was applied to all combinations of species and device. Figure 11 shows the means plot of the velocity obtained with time lag correction deduced from equation (1) and Table 8, for each length and for four examples of species and device combination. The velocity shows an approximately constant value for the three lengths in all combinations of species and device. There is no statistically significant relationship between velocity and length, at a confidence level of 95%, because P -values (0.0886 to 0.9776, mean value 0.5026) are greater than 0.05.

Figure 11. Means plot of velocity ANOVA (including time lag correction) for length (1.52, 2.52 and 3.52 m) in crossed measurements corresponding to four cases of species and device combination

3.4 Influence of method on velocity measurement

Previous sections show the procedure for the determination of time lag correction for end-to-end, surface and crossed ToF measurement in order to obtain the velocity independent of length. Table 9 shows the differences between velocities obtained from the surface and crossed procedures compared with end-to-end measurement.

The velocity $V_{0,cor}$ is the velocity corrected by time lag, obtained as l/b from equation (1) and table 4; $V_{se,cor}$ and $V_{sf,cor}$ are the surface velocities (edges and faces, respectively) corrected by time lag, obtained as l/b from equation (1) and table 7; and, $V_{ce,cor}$ and $V_{cf,cor}$ are the crossed velocities (edges and faces, respectively) corrected by time lag, obtained as l/b from equation (1) and table 8.

The surface and crossed velocities have slightly lower values than end-to-end velocities. The differences between velocities obtained by end-to-end measurement and surface or crossed measurement are slight (equal to or less than 4.4% on average). The lowest differences were obtained with the MST Fakopp device (equal to or less than 0.7% on average). The two ultrasonic devices (Sylvatest Duo and USLab) have similar differences compared with end-to-end measurement. Although these velocity ratios differ depending on species, the differences are small. It can be concluded that the velocity obtained by means of surface or crossed in situ measurement could be corrected to the reference procedure (end-to-end) multiplying it by the corresponding factor for each device, and it is practically independent on species.

Table 9. Ratios between velocities corrected by time lag for species, device and for each sensor positioning.

Species	Parameter	Device		
		Sylvatest Duo	USLab	MST Fakopp
radiata p.	$V_{0,cor}$ (m s ⁻¹)	5014	5478	5232
	$V_{0,cor}/V_{se,cor}$	1.034	1.051	1.000
	$V_{0,cor}/V_{sf,cor}$	1.035	1.026	1.008
	$V_{0,cor}/V_{ce,cor}$	1.026	1.033	1.000
	$V_{0,cor}/V_{cf,cor}$	1.034	1.023	1.001
	mean	1.032	1.033	1.002
Scots p.	$V_{0,cor}$ (m s ⁻¹)	5104	5510	5118
	$V_{0,cor}/V_{se,cor}$	1.032	1.038	1.013
	$V_{0,cor}/V_{sf,cor}$	1.014	1.018	1.004
	$V_{0,cor}/V_{ce,cor}$	1.017	1.017	0.988
	$V_{0,cor}/V_{cf,cor}$	1.022	1.022	1.001
	mean	1.021	1.024	1.001
laricio p.	$V_{0,cor}$ (m s ⁻¹)	4807	5308	4976
	$V_{0,cor}/V_{se,cor}$	1.045	1.053	1.010
	$V_{0,cor}/V_{sf,cor}$	1.024	1.040	1.016
	$V_{0,cor}/V_{ce,cor}$	1.015	1.038	0.988
	$V_{0,cor}/V_{cf,cor}$	1.034	1.046	1.015
	mean	1.029	1.044	1.007
maritime p.	$V_{0,cor}$ (m s ⁻¹)	4144	4455	4353
	$V_{0,cor}/V_{se,cor}$	1.007	1.027	0.991
	$V_{0,cor}/V_{sf,cor}$	1.024	1.038	1.002
	$V_{0,cor}/V_{ce,cor}$	1.025	1.035	0.992
	$V_{0,cor}/V_{cf,cor}$	1.014	1.030	1.002
	mean	1.018	1.032	0.997

3.5 Modulus of elasticity prediction

The dynamic MOE, E_{dyn} , was obtained according to equation (3), where V_i is velocity obtained for the different procedures ($V_0, V_{\text{se}}, V_{\text{sf}}, V_{\text{ce}}$ and V_{cf}), including the time lag correction of ToF, and ρ_i is the density of each piece.

$$E_{\text{dyn}} = V_i^2 \cdot \rho_i \quad (3)$$

Linear regressions were established between dynamic MOEs and the static MOE, E , obtained according to section 2.4, equation (4).

$$E = a + b \cdot E_{\text{dyn}} \quad (4)$$

These linear regressions were done for each device and including all species. A previous multiple linear regression between dynamic MOEs and the static MOE considering the species parameter as qualitative variable, showed that in most cases species had a P -value greater than 0.05, so it could be removed from the model. It must be noted that these calculations were made for the 3 m length pieces, due to the fact that MOE was obtained at this length. Table 10 shows the coefficients of equation (4) for each procedure and device. It can be seen that the determination coefficient and the standard error are similar in all cases (0.76 - 0.85, and 911 – 1095 N mm⁻², respectively).

Table 10. Linear regression models for Static MOE vs. dynamic MOE (equation 4) for each measurement procedure and device.

Procedure	Device	a (N mm ⁻²)	b	r ²	Standard error (N mm ⁻²)
End to end (0)	Sylvatest	-743	0.9184	0.85	913
	USLab	-419	0.7483	0.85	911
	MST	-1384	0.9131	0.81	1003
Surface edges (se)	Sylvatest	122	0.9027	0.78	1095
	USLab	172	0.7629	0.82	997
	MST	-949	0.8881	0.76	1130
Surface faces (sf)	Sylvatest	-422	0.9284	0.85	914
	USLab	257	0.7362	0.83	955
	MST	-1315	0.9155	0.81	1020
Crossed edges (ce)	Sylvatest	-50	0.8867	0.82	974
	USLab	664	0.7019	0.80	1026
	MST	1080	0.8674	0.79	1053
Crossed faces (cf)	Sylvatest	-390	0.9291	0.83	958
	USLab	446	0.7210	0.83	967
	MST	-871	0.8782	0.80	1025

Table 11 shows the mean values of dynamic MOE obtained for each species and device according to equation (3) for end-to-end measurement and for 3 m length pieces. They were calculated from the velocity (with ToF corrected by the corresponding time lag)

and the density of each piece. Furthermore, the ratios with respect to the static MOE included in table 3 are shown. The dynamic MOEs were higher than static MOEs, with a ratio from approximately 1.1 to 1.5, depending on the species and device. Other work (Casado et al. 2012) showed an average ratio of 1.44 for poplar using the Sylvatest Duo.

It can be noticed that this ratio is in general slightly greater than the ratio observed with respect to dynamic MOE obtained by means of vibration analysis. Ratios of 1.14 and 1.12 were deduced for longitudinal and transverse vibration in radiata pine (Arriaga et al. 2012) and 1.13, 1.04 and 1.03 for radiata, Scots and laricio pine, respectively, in longitudinal vibration (Arriaga et al. 2014), and 1.14 for poplar in longitudinal vibration (Casado et al. 2012).

Table 11. Average values of dynamic MOE obtained by species and device, and ratios to static MOE (calculated for end-to-end measurement and for 3 m long pieces).

Species	Sylvatest		USLab		MST	
	E _{dyn} - COV (N mm ⁻² - %)	E _{dyn} /E	E _{dyn} - COV (N/mm ⁻² - %)	E _{dyn} /E	E _{dyn} - COV (N mm ⁻² - %)	E _{dyn} /E
radiata	13160 - 14.2	1.225	15791 - 13.8	1.469	14139 - 13.8	1.316
Scots	13633 - 11.6	1.158	16062 - 11.3	1.364	13709 - 10.9	1.164
laricio	12983 - 17.4	1.094	15953 - 16.7	1.344	14050 - 16.4	1.184
maritime	10201 - 17.8	1.195	11799 - 18.1	1.383	11.174 - 17.6	1.309
mean		1.168		1.390		1.243

4. Conclusions

A procedure is proposed to obtain the time lag in time-of-flight of wave propagation using three devices in four coniferous species. Several times-of-flight should be measured in each piece, over a distance of at least 1.5 m, approximately.

The in-situ measuring procedures of time of flight, as is the case with surface and crossed measurements are also valid to obtain the time lag and velocity independent of length. The differences between velocity obtained by end-to-end measurement and surface or crossed measurement are equal or less than 4.4% on average. The influence of species is weak and a simple factor correction for velocity in each device can be proposed.

The static modulus of elasticity estimation from dynamic modulus of elasticity by a linear regression showed a good determination coefficient (0.76 – 0.85) for the three devices and is species independent. It is remarkable to note that these correlations have similar determination coefficients for all the procedures tested (end-to-end, surface and crossed measurements).

The dynamic moduli of elasticity obtained are, as was expected, higher than the static modulus of elasticity. The ratio varies from 1.1 to 1.5 depending on species and device.

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